

Effect of Gaze Visualization on Task Efficiency and User Behavior for Guidance Scenarios in Co-Located AR Collaboration

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ABSTRACT

Augmented Reality (AR)-enabled collaboration enhances contextual guidance in shared environments, where unambiguous cues are essential, for swift and accurate task completion. Gaze-based cues offer clear, non-verbal indication of intent, reducing interaction ambiguity. While prior research has studied the effectiveness of gaze-based visualization in scenarios where collaborators share the same level of knowledge, less attention has been shown to guidance scenarios, where one user provides task-related information to another. Existing studies often focus on task outcomes (e.g., completion time, error rate) without analyzing gaze data to gain further insight into user behavior and attention. This study leverages gaze-based cues as an active means of communication in guidance scenarios, assessing their impact on both task performance and user behavior through gaze data analysis. The developed system incorporates gaze-based visualizations, including dynamic representations of gaze behavior, to deliver task-critical guidance. These are compared to verbal instructions using quantitative metrics for task effectiveness and gaze analysis, alongside subjective feedback, to determine whether they reduce ambiguity and enhance collaboration. Our study showed that gaze-based visualizations significantly reduced task related errors, with contextual triggered cues offering the best balance between speed and correctness. Gaze analysis revealed that gaze-based visualizations effectively directed participants' attention to task-relevant areas, reducing unnecessary visual exploration. Participants reported lower perceived workload in gaze-based conditions, further supporting their effectiveness in enhancing collaboration and reducing ambiguity.

Index Terms: Human-centered computing—Human computer interaction (HCI)—Interaction paradigms—Mixed augmented reality; Human-centered computing—Human computer interaction (HCI)—HCI design and evaluation methods— User studies

1 INTRODUCTION

Extended Reality (XR) environments have introduced new opportunities for collaboration, enabling seamless interaction and communication. Main research challenges focus on how users perceive collaborators' intentions and actions [16]. The critical role of communication cues in supporting effective collaboration is central to this research area [7], shaped by factors such as the specific environment and task context, level of artificiality and range of interactions [36]. Effective communication cues, in the form of visual elements such as hand gestures and gaze, play a crucial role in enhancing collaboration by enriching interactions and improving situational awareness among participants [25]. Gaze cues have been utilized in remote collaboration to enhance visual awareness and accelerate task completion through shared gaze visualization [20].

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Building on this, studies have gone one step further by leveraging gaze behavior visualizations, demonstrating that combining color and shape changes in gaze interfaces effectively convey joint attention and improves mutual communication [23, 24].

Figure 1: The two users in the shared AR environment, both wearing Microsoft HoloLens 2 devices.

While prior research has demonstrated the benefits of shared gaze cues in remote collaboration for improving mutual awareness and task understanding [8, 21], co-located scenarios, where collaborators operate within the same physical space, have been less explored in utilizing gaze visualization [12]. Although AR-based co-located collaboration has been deployed in various domains—such as medicine [13], veterinarian training [40], industrial assembly [37], and puzzle-solving [9], these studies emphasize the potential of AR for teamwork, without incorporating gaze cues. Existing work on gaze-based communication in co-located settings often assumes scenarios where collaborators share equal task knowledge [14, 22]. However, there is limited exploration of gaze visualizations in guidance scenarios where collaborators have differing levels of knowledge. Tasks that involve searching and placing, where one collaborator provides instructions and another executes them, require efficient communication cues to share task knowledge seamlessly while minimizing the ambiguity inherent in verbal instructions. In that context, we pose the question: *How do gaze-based visual cues compare to traditional verbal commands in facilitating task-related information sharing in collocated collaboration settings, both in terms of task efficiency and user behavior?*

To address this question, we developed a system that integrates gaze-based input as a primary communication cue for task-related information. The system visualizes the collaborator's gaze behavior as a ray terminating at a pointer within the user's task area, with the gaze behavior dynamically visualized to indicate focus. The task involves the collaborator guiding the user in positioning virtual 3D objects at predefined positions. To evaluate the effectiveness of gaze-based visual cues compared to traditional verbal commands, we go past subjective measures (i.e. questionnaires), by incorporating gaze-based metrics for post-task analysis. By recording and analyzing gaze data, we assess how visual attention is distributed across the task environment in relation to the form of guidance. This approach offers quantitative insights that complement qualitative observations,

enabling a more comprehensive evaluation of the role of gaze-based visualization in facilitating task-related information sharing during co-located collaboration. Our contributions include:

- A system that integrates real-time gaze-based input, dynamically visualized to convey task-related context, providing an intuitive method for task guidance in co-located collaborative environments.
- Metric-based evaluation, analyzing gaze data to quantify and extract results about visual attention distribution and its correlation with the form of the provided instructions.
- A comparative study of communication methods investigating the impact of shared gaze visual cues and traditional verbal commands in guidance scenarios, evaluating their impact on task efficiency and user behavior in guidance scenarios within co-located collaboration settings.

2 RELATED WORK

2.1 Guidance in AR environments

AR can be useful in disambiguating instructions by overlaying task-relevant digital content in the physical space. Static overlays such as 3D augmented maps [35], arrows, lines or object highlights have been used to improve task localization and efficiency [17]. AR-enabled attention guiding mechanisms like semi-transparent waves or peripheral feedback, are effective in guiding users toward task-critical elements while minimizing cognitive overload [33, 34]. Beyond abstract 3D content, AR systems have incorporated interactive communication cues, like gaze and gesture proxies, to align attention and improve situational awareness in educational scenarios [39]. In collaborative settings where verbal instructions are insufficient due to partner occlusion, shared hand gestures, along with 3D markers have been employed to enhance task coordination [15]. Systems combining gaze and gesture cues with live 3D panoramas enhance mutual understanding and task performance by creating intuitive shared workspaces [8]. Gaze-based pointers in AR systems improve co-presence and streamline collaboration by allowing users to follow their partner's visual focus and align on task-critical areas [26]. Taking inspiration from past work, our system uses dynamic gaze visualizations as active deictic signals, evaluated to assess their impact through both task-based outcomes and user behavior analysis.

2.2 Visualization of Gaze Cues and Gaze Behaviour in Collaboration

Shared gaze visualization leverages modern Head Mounted Displays' (HMDs) eye-tracking capabilities to display each person's gaze in a shared space, enabling gaze-based pointing and focus sharing to enhance communication, and task coordination [12], while reducing cognitive load and accelerating task completion [20]. Collaboration systems that incorporate gaze behavioral cues have shown potential to improve remote collaboration experiences. In Jing et al. [24] a system was developed that enabled the sharing of gaze behaviors between a local host in AR and a remote collaborator in Virtual Reality (VR), to convey joint attention and notify collaborators when their gazes coincided, reducing cognitive effort. Expanding on this, designs incorporating different gaze interfaces with changes in color or shape, proved to be effective in sharing attention with combined color and shape changes being the most preferred [23]. A study visualizing gaze cues near the user's focus showed reduction in attention division and improvement in task understanding compared to displaying cues based on body position [21].

While shared gaze visualization in remote collaboration is heavily explored, researchers are now examining co-located setups to address challenges in aligning attention and intention without relying on verbal or physical cues [22]. Gaze data visualizations serve as

visual attention indicators, helping paired users align their focus on the shared task [41]. Bi-directional gaze visualizations with integrated gaze behavior, outperform non-collaborative visualizations (display solely self/user cues) in conveying intention, while the incorporation of spatial elements in gaze interfaces (i.e. gaze direction), induces collaborator's mutual reaction with a relatively low mental effort [22]. Gaze behaviors visualized through methods like gaze triggering, where the visualization appears only after a user focuses on a point, allow collaborators to intuitively interpret each other's focus and intentions, fostering better alignment and reducing ambiguity during joint tasks [14]. While past work has demonstrated the efficacy of gaze-based visualizations in use cases with the same level of knowledge between collaborators, less attention has been shown to asymmetric pair tasks, where collaborators possess differing levels of knowledge. To address this gap, our work explores the use of AR gaze visualizations and gaze-sharing strategies in guidance scenarios, focusing on situations in which one user provides task-related information to another.

2.3 Evaluation in collaborative AR

Collaborative-centric evaluations that include contextualized data collection for insights into user interaction and performance are essential for advancing AR research [30]. While AR research has traditionally relied on subjective measures, such as questionnaires and interviews, advancements in wearable AR technology [28] have facilitated a more thorough quantitative analysis through modality tracking [38]. Recent studies emphasize combining subjective methods with objective metrics, such as gaze data, motion tracking, and task completion analysis, to better understand collaborative processes [31]. Incorporating eye-tracking and task-based metrics can enhance evaluation, enabling researchers to assess visual attention [29].

Existing work in co-located guidance scenarios, where one collaborator provides instructions to another, have not fully explored gaze analysis. Chen et al. [11] investigated two distinct types of gaze cues in a scenario involving a pointing task. Their study revealed that that direct pointing improved task performance, while trailing effects enhanced social presence and was preferred. Similarly, Bragger et al. [10] investigated various gaze visualization prototypes, including gaze lines and gaze cursors, in navigation tasks. While findings highlighted the promise of gaze-guided solutions for enhancing communication and reducing errors, such research focused primarily, apart from subjective metrics, on task completion times and task errors without delving into sophisticated gaze analysis. In contrast, Acar et al. [5] delved further into gaze analysis but focused specifically on a 2D monitor setup for intraoperative guidance in kidney stone surgeries, limiting the task area. Additionally, the task utilized gaze assistance complementary to verbal communication, which may not fully capture the potential of gaze-guided solutions. Pathmanatha et al. [32] investigated the effects of AR interfaces with situated information on co-located collaborative tasks, showing enhanced focus and reduced reliance on physical instructions. While their study analyzed gaze data to assess attention patterns, gaze was not used as a means for providing instructions, as gaze rays were only included for illustration purposes, and the scenario focused on collaborators with the same level of knowledge, rather than one guiding the other. Our work focuses on leveraging gaze-based cues as an active means of communication in guidance scenarios, while also evaluating their impact on user behaviour by conducting an analysis of visual attention.

3 SYSTEM DESIGN

Our system design reflects instructional scenarios, that involve directing a user to complete a goal-oriented activity. Based on the *reference-action sequence* framework [6], the setup involves one

Figure 2: Instructor's gaze visualized in the task space.

user making a reference to an object and the other user performing an action on it. In such scenarios, where ambiguities are likely to arise, gaze can play a crucial role as a non-verbal tool for disambiguation, enhancing referential communication [18], by providing clear, non-verbal indications of focus [22] and consequently, facilitating precise deictic actions.

Besides gaze, hand gestures are also a common means of referential communication in co-located settings. However, they are not without limitations. For instance, when a user's hands are occupied or obscured by specialized equipment, gaze visualization serves as a viable alternative, enabling users to direct attention without requiring manual actions. Additionally, differences in viewing perspectives between collaborators, which have been shown to cause challenges in remote settings [27], can similarly occur in co-located settings when collaborators have differing lines of sight. This can lead to ambiguities in interpreting the direction or target of a pointing gesture. Gaze visualizations can compensate for these limitations, reducing physical or cognitive demands in communication. Furthermore, they offer an inclusive alternative for users with temporary or permanent disabilities, allowing effective participation in collaborative tasks without relying on speech or manual gestures to convey attention or focus. Taking into account these aspects, we focus on utilizing gaze as the primary means of communication in our study.

In that context, we developed a collaborative task, where one user provides guidance, and the other executes it, with the aim to test how gaze-based cues affect task efficiency by reducing ambiguities during object selection and placement activities.

3.1 Collaborative Task and Experimental Conditions

The collaborative task involves two users in a shared virtual environment, each wearing the same HMD, in our case Microsoft's Hololens 2 device (Figure 1). The task requires one user to pick up 3D objects from a diverse set arranged on a horizontal surface and place them on designated virtual shelves. The user performing these actions relies on instructions provided by the other user, who acts as the instructor and determines which objects to select and where they should be placed. The instructor's gaze is visualized in the shared environment as a ray extending from their head to a pointer (Figure 2). The pointer dynamically changes in size and color after 0.8s of gaze fixation on a 3D object (Figure 4a). This 0.8s fixation duration was determined through testing, reflecting the balance between speed and accuracy of selection. We decided to include the ray in the visualization to improve spatial understanding of the instructor's gaze direction [22]. Although bi-directional visualizations have been shown to effectively convey intention and focus in tasks where users have the same level of knowledge [22], testing revealed that it was distracting in our guidance task, therefore, the user's gaze is not visualized in both point of views (POV). Conversely, in the instructor's POV, only the pointer of their gaze is displayed as a subtle

helper, materializing their gaze behavior (Figure 3b). Additionally, the instructor can place a 3D arrow annotation on target shelves using a gaze-pinch gesture (Figure 4b). After designating the shelf, the instructor selects an object from the set using their gaze. When the instructor's gaze dwells on an object, the user interprets this as the object to be picked up and places it on the indicated shelf. From a group of 16 objects, 8 are chosen to be placed.

In order to understand the impact of the gaze visualization on task progress and user behavior, we determined three experimental conditions, the Constant Gaze (CG) condition, in which the instructor gaze visualization with the previously mentioned characteristics (pointer and ray) was continuously visible throughout the task, the Triggered Gaze (TG) condition, in which the gaze visualization (pointer and ray) appeared only when the instructor was fixating on an object and the Verbal Instructions (VI) condition, where guidance was provided exclusively through verbal instructions, with no gaze-based cues or annotations (baseline condition). The TG condition was included to examine whether limiting the continuous display of gaze visualization reduces cognitive load and to assess whether a constant gaze visualization may be distracting during the task.

(a) User's POV

(b) Instructor's POV

Figure 3: The AR environment of the task, with a simultaneous depiction of both POVs. (a) The user's POV, depicting the instructor's gaze interface in the CG condition. (b) The instructor sees only the pointer of their own gaze.

3.2 Implementation

The system was developed in Unity [3] for the *Universal Windows Platform* [4]. We used *Mixed Reality Toolkit 3* [1] for the implementation. The two devices are connected on the same local network via WiFi, with a Peer-to-Peer (P2P) parameterized network topology with one device acting as a host and the other as a client. Networking logic is handled by Unity's Netcode for GameObjects [2]. The

Figure 4: (a) Visualization of the instructor's gaze fixation. (b) 3D arrow placed on a shelf by the instructor to annotate it.

alignment of the two devices' coordinate systems is implemented via QR code tracking, establishing a common coordinate system at the code's real-world location. Upon launch, both users scan the QR code, to ensure consistency in the spatial placement of the objects and the users. The system collects eye-tracking data throughout the task progress. To quantify visual attention, defined as fixation of gaze on task-relevant areas, we identified virtual Areas of Interest (AOI) within the task space. These AOIs include the 3D objects on the horizontal plane, the virtual shelves where objects are placed, and in the CG and TG conditions, the collaborator (i.e. instructor). Although we do not anticipate significant gaze data focused on the collaborator due to the spatial arrangement of the task, this AOI is included for completeness. Gaze data is recorded when the user's gaze enters the corresponding colliders, with the system logging the duration of gaze on these colliders. Post-task, the recorded gaze data are aggregated for each AOI, and the relative fixation durations are calculated as the proportion of fixation time on each AOI relative to the overall task time.

4 USER STUDY

The main goal of the study is to examine how gaze-based information sharing affects task efficiency and behavior. This focus is inherently tied to the user's perspective, as they are the recipient of the instructor's gaze-based cues and the primary actor responsible for executing the task. The effectiveness of gaze-based communication is ultimately reflected in how well the user interprets and responds to the cues, making their perspective the most relevant for assessing task efficiency and visual attention. Therefore, we decided to gather qualitative and quantitative metrics only from the user side, since according to task design we consider the instructors gaze behaviour relatively consistent and controlled across all conditions.

4.1 Participants

The study included 17 participants, of which 10 were female and 7 male. Participants' ages were between 18-44 years old. 7 participants reported no previous experience with AR headsets, 6 had limited experience (they had tried an AR headset briefly), 1 that they had moderate experience (they occasionally used AR headsets), and 3 experts. The instructor's role was carried out by the same person throughout the study to maintain consistency.

4.2 Metrics

We gathered quantitative metrics about task efficiency, which are task completion time and task correctness. Task correctness was measured as the percentage of objects correctly selected and placed by the user during the task. Errors were defined as either selecting the wrong object and/or placing an object on the incorrect shelf. Gaze data were recorded according to the procedure mentioned in the *Implementation* section. Regarding subjective feedback, we used the NASA TLX questionnaire [19] to evaluate perceived workload. We also included a general questionnaire to gather participant feedback on overall preference and their ratings on aspects of the conditions. Participants answered the following items on a 7-point Likert scale: *Q1-The instructions were accurately represented to me*, *Q2-This form of visualisation is effective*, *Q3-This form of visualisation is engaging*, *Q4-How aware were you of your instructors presence in the AR environment?*. Q2, Q3 were derived from a previous study [22].

4.3 Procedure

We followed a within-subject design. Participants were briefed on the study procedure and wore the Microsoft HoloLens 2. Each performed the eye calibration process provided by the device's system. To familiarize themselves with the AR environment and the task, participants first performed a trial session. Once ready to begin, participants initiated each session by pressing a button in the AR environment. The order of the experimental conditions was counterbalanced. In the VI condition, participants were instructed to proceed in one of two ways if they were unsure about the verbal instructions given: either continue with their best guess regarding the correct object or shelf, or ask clarifying questions. In the CG and TG conditions, once an annotation on the shelf was placed by the instructor, it remained visible for 4 seconds. This duration was chosen based on internal testing, as longer display time could interfere with the process of subsequent placements (overlapping annotations). After the end of the experiment, participants answered the questionnaires.

5 RESULTS

In this section, we present the findings of the study, focusing on task efficiency, gaze analysis, and subjective feedback. Statistical analysis was performed using repeated-measures ANOVA to evaluate task efficiency and gaze based metrics.

5.1 Task efficiency

As previously mentioned, task efficiency is evaluated using task completion time and correctness. The completion times of the three conditions are shown in Figure 5. The TG condition recorded the lowest mean completion time ($\mu=132.9$ s, $\sigma=29.7$ s), followed by VI ($\mu=139.8$ s, $\sigma=18.7$ s). The CG condition had the highest mean completion time ($\mu=142.8$ s, $\sigma=34.4$ s). Repeated-measures ANOVA revealed no statistically significant differences between the conditions ($F_{2,32} = 0.734, p = 0.488, \eta_g^2 = 0.022$). Task correctness scores can be seen on Table 1. A repeated-measures ANOVA showed a statistically significant effect of condition on correctness ($F_{2,32} = 12.82, p < 0.001, \eta_g^2 = 0.299$). Post-hoc pairwise comparisons (Bonferroni-corrected) showed that correctness scores for the CG and TG conditions were significantly higher than those for the

VI condition ($p < 0.001, p = 0.011$, respectively). However, no significant difference was observed between CG and TG ($p = 1.000$). Considering the relationship between task completion time and correctness, while the CG condition recorded a higher mean completion time compared to the VI condition, it also achieved higher correctness scores from VI. This suggests that the ambiguity of verbal instructions in the VI condition has led participants to make more errors despite completing the task more quickly. The TG condition demonstrated the best overall balance, achieving the lowest mean completion time while maintaining a high correctness score.

Figure 5: Box plots of task completion times of the three conditions, with individual data points.

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of Task Correctness

Condition	Mean (%)	SD (%)
CG	97.05	9.41
TG	97.05	5.47
VI	80.88	17.74

5.2 Gaze-based metrics

Relative fixation durations for each AOI (3D objects, virtual shelves, and the instructor), were calculated as the proportion in percent of time spent gazing on each AOI relative to the overall task time. The results are presented in Figure 6. In the VI condition, the instructor was not immersed in the AR environment, therefore no fixation durations were recorded for that AOI in that condition. Across the three conditions participants spent the highest gaze time on the 3D objects, CG ($\mu=29.74\%$, $\sigma=8.22\%$), TG ($\mu=30.5\%$, $\sigma=8.87\%$), VI ($\mu=42.06\%$, $\sigma=9.65\%$). Relative fixations on shelves were overall lower, CG ($\mu=16.92\%$, $\sigma=6.03\%$), TG ($\mu=13.23\%$, $\sigma=3.74\%$), VI ($\mu=14.03\%$, $\sigma=4.55\%$). As was observed during the experiments, participants rarely looked at the instructor during the task, CG ($\mu=0.58\%$, $\sigma=0.71\%$), TG ($\mu=1.03\%$, $\sigma=0.78\%$).

We excluded the instructor AOI from the CG and TG conditions in order to have a balanced repeated-measures ANOVA design, and it revealed significant main effects of both condition ($F_{5,80} = 54.72, p < 0.001, \eta_p^2 = 0.77$) and AOI ($F_{1,16} = 89.59, p < 0.001, \eta_p^2 = 0.85$), as well as significant interaction between condition and AOI ($F_{5,80} = 58.07, p < 0.001, \eta_p^2 = 0.78$). Post-hoc pairwise comparisons (Bonferroni-corrected) showed that fixations on the Objects were significantly higher in the VI condition than both the CG ($p < 0.001$) and TG ($p < 0.001$) conditions. Similarly, for

the Shelves AOI, fixation durations were significantly lower in the TG condition compared to both CG ($p < 0.001$) and VI ($p < 0.001$). These results indicate that the VI condition resulted in highest visual exploration times of the horizontal task space, as participants spent more time searching for the correct object without the immediate guidance provided by visual indications, such as those in the CG and TG conditions. For the Shelves AOI, fixation durations were lower in the TG condition compared to CG and VI.

5.3 User Feedback

Average NASA TLX scores across the three conditions are presented in Figure 7. For mental demand, CG had the lowest average score ($\mu=2.94$, $\sigma=1.25$), followed by TG ($\mu=3.06$, $\sigma=1.60$), while VI had the highest score ($\mu=3.29$, $\sigma=1.86$), indicating that verbal instructions had a higher cognitive load on participants. A similar trend was observed for frustration, where CG scored the lowest ($\mu=2.94$, $\sigma=2.24$), followed by TG ($\mu=3.12$, $\sigma=2.44$). VI scored ($\mu=3.76$, $\sigma=2.08$), suggesting that the lack of ambiguity in gaze-based conditions reduced frustration levels compared to verbal instructions. Interestingly, participants reported lower temporal demand for VI ($\mu=3.65$, $\sigma=2.26$) compared to TG ($\mu=3.88$, $\sigma=2.09$) and CG ($\mu=4.11$, $\sigma=2.26$). This may reflect how the task was structured in the gaze-based conditions, where the arrow annotations disappeared after a few seconds, potentially creating stress for participants to quickly act on the visual cues.

Physical demand scored lowest of all aspects with the gazed-based conditions (CG, TG) scoring the same ($\mu=2.53$, $\sigma=1.28$ and $\sigma=1.77$ respectively), while VI scored slightly higher ($\mu=2.88$, $\sigma=1.36$), reflecting the minimal physical effort required for the task. For effort, VI scored highest ($\mu=3.47$, $\sigma=2.00$), followed closely by CG ($\mu=3.29$, $\sigma=1.31$) and TG ($\mu=3.24$, $\sigma=1.60$). The similar effort ratings suggest that, while verbal instructions influenced participants' workload, all conditions demanded comparable levels of attention and action to complete the task. Finally, performance had the highest difference between the gaze-based conditions and the VI, with both CG and TG scoring the same ($\mu=7.53$, $\sigma=3.02$ and $\sigma=2.76$ respectively), against VI ($\mu=6.23$, $\sigma=2.68$). This highlights the effectiveness of gaze-based cues in enabling participants to feel more confident in their performance. Overall, the results indicate that gaze-based conditions show potential to reduce workload and frustration while enhancing task performance and user confidence.

Regarding the rest of the questions presented to participants, a 7-point Likert scale was used, with 1 indicating "strongly disagree" and 7 indicating "strongly agree". For *Q1-The instructions were accurately represented to me*, CG condition received the most consistent high ratings, with 15 participants answering with the highest score ("strongly agree"), and the remaining two scoring it with 5 and 6. Similarly, the TG condition had 13 participants stating "strongly agree", 3 scoring it a 6, and 1 giving it a 5. In contrast, the VI condition showed greater variability in responses: while 10 participants answered with "strongly agree", 3 participants gave it the lowest scores (1 and 2), and the rest rated it in the middle range (3–6). This indicates that verbal instructions were perceived as less reliable and clear, likely due to the absence of the deictic precision of the visual guidance. *Q2-This form of visualization is effective*, *Q3-This form of visualization is engaging* and *Q4-How aware were you of your instructors presence in the AR environment?* were evaluated only for the CG and TG conditions. For Q2, the CG condition received the highest score from 8 participants, while 5 participants rated it a 6, 3 gave it a 5, and 1 participant scored it a 4. In comparison, the TG condition results were slightly more varied, with 5 participants stating "strongly agree", 6 participants scoring it a 6, 5 participants a 5, and 1 participant rating it a 3. Both conditions were perceived as effective, but TG's slightly more varied ratings could reflect the challenge some participants faced in adapting to the triggered visualization, as it was not always continuously visible. Q3 scored

Figure 6: Box plots of relative fixation durations (%) on each defined AOI across the three conditions, with individual data points.

Figure 7: NASA TLX Scores by Condition (1-very low, 10-very high).

the same average for both conditions. For CG, 10 participants rated it the highest, 5 gave it a 6, and 1 gave it a 4. For TG, 9 participants rated it the highest, 6 gave it a 6, and 2 rated it a 4 and 5, respectively, indicating that both conditions were similarly engaging overall. CG scored slightly higher than TG on average for Q4, with 11 participants stating "strongly agree" compared to 9 participants for TG. The remaining scores were similarly distributed across both conditions, which means that both conditions were perceived as effective in fostering awareness of the instructor's presence, with CG slightly more favored in this regard.

Finally, participants were asked to indicate their overall preference between the three conditions. CG was the most preferred, with 8 participants selecting it as their favorite, followed by TG, preferred by 6 participants. Interestingly, 3 participants expressed a preference for the VI condition. These results suggest a general favorability toward gaze-based conditions, though very few participants still found VI condition more suitable, potentially reflecting challenges with the AR setup, like the timing of triggered annotations, or difficulties in interpreting the visual cues.

6 DISCUSSION

The presented study revealed an advantage for the gaze-based visualizations compared to verbal commands in facilitating task-related information sharing. Task efficiency was assessed not only in terms of low completion times, but also in the ability to complete the task with minimal errors. Initially, we thought that the VI condition, which relies heavily on verbal communication, would result in longer completion times, particularly because the similarity between certain 3D objects was intentionally designed to necessitate clarification and the order of the shelves (e.g., bottom-to-top or top-to-bottom) was often misinterpreted. Although additional verbal communication was often required during the experiments to clarify object selection, the highest completion times resulted in the CG condition. A contributing factor to this, is the fact that since the gaze ray was constantly visible in the CG condition, participants appeared to spend extra time ensuring the instructor's selection was correct before taking action, which added delays especially compared to the TG condition, where gaze cues were only visible during fixation on the task-relevant objects, allowing for more immediate reactions. Interaction errors from the instructor in the AR environment, may also contributed to this. However, the results showed that while VI achieved slightly faster average completion times than the CG condition, it came at the cost of significantly higher error rates. This suggests that participants in the VI condition may have prioritized speed over accuracy, leading to more mistakes despite the ability to have additional verbal communication. An example of this was the frequent misinterpretation of the "last shelf," where participants often failed to notice the actual last shelf and mistakenly placed objects on the second-to-last shelf. This issue was not non-existent when there was visual indication of the correct shelves. In contrast, both gaze-based conditions (CG and TG) demonstrated high correctness scores, confirming the use of visual cues in reducing ambiguity.

Regarding gaze data analysis, we anticipated that participants in the VI condition would spend more time fixated on the objects to disambiguate verbal instructions and make the selection, which was reflected in the metric results, indicating the additional visual exploration required in the absence of visual guidance. As for the shelves, the VI condition did not produce the longer relative fixation durations one might expect, likely due to the aforementioned trade-off between speed and accuracy, where participants prioritized completing the task quickly at the expense of precision. Between the CG and TG conditions, object relative fixation durations were

similar. However, durations on shelves were lower in TG than CG. In CG, the constant gaze ray, often appearing in front of the shelves, may have acted as a persistent distraction. This constant presence likely drew participants' attention to the shelves more frequently, even when the task did not require it, leading to increased relative fixation durations on this AOI. We did not consider the instructor AOI as an important area for relative fixations, given the nature of the collaboration setup and the spatial arrangement of the task environment, which naturally minimized the need for participants to visually engage with the instructor.

The NASA TLX results show that gaze-based conditions reduced perceived workload compared to VI. Participants reported lower mental demand and frustration in CG and TG, highlighting the use of gaze-based cues in reducing cognitive effort. Although, CG showed higher temporal demand compared to TG and VI, likely due to the constant presence of gaze rays, which may have distracted the participants from focusing on task-critical areas more, or take notice of the annotation, it was voted as the most preferred condition. VI, on the other hand, showed the highest frustration, mental and effort scores, reflecting the cognitive burden imposed by ambiguous verbal instructions. This was reflected in participants' comments, such as: "Verbal instructions were more stressful because there were moments when I was unsure how to proceed with the task."

In addition to workload-related challenges, hardware limitations were also noted by participants. Several commented on the small field of view of the device, stating: "I had to move my head a lot because I couldn't see all the shelves and objects, so I wasn't so fast." Furthermore, design choices, such as the time limit for the red arrow annotations in the TG and CG conditions, introduced additional cognitive pressure. As one participant noted: "The time limit for the appearance of the red arrows is low and made me focus a lot in order to not miss it."

Regarding the stated research question, the results clearly demonstrate that gaze-based cues are more effective than verbal instructions in reducing errors, enhancing task efficiency, and lowering perceived workload. While the VI condition allowed for faster task completion in some instances, this came at the expense of accuracy and increased cognitive strain. Additionally, gaze-based conditions effectively directed participants' visual attention to task-critical points in the environment, reducing unnecessary exploration. This was particularly evident in the TG condition, where the interface design minimized visual clutter and efficiently guided attention to relevant elements, without causing distractions.

7 CONCLUSION

A co-located AR collaboration system was implemented, utilizing the gaze as the primary communication cue to facilitate task-related information sharing in guidance scenarios. The study that was conducted, highlighted the advantages of gaze-based cues compared to verbal commands in such settings. Both CG and TG conditions proved effective in reducing ambiguity, improving task correctness, and lowering perceived cognitive workload compared to verbal instructions. However, we consider the interface design to have played a role in shaping user performance. While the CG condition provided consistent visual guidance, and was overall preferred in user feedback, its constant visibility occasionally introduced distractions. On the other hand, TG offered an efficient approach by directing participants' attention only when necessary, achieving a better balance between qualitative and quantitative metrics. The overall results of the VI condition, underscored the limitations of relying solely on verbal instructions in tasks requiring disambiguation.

Our study focused exclusively on the user's perspective, assuming consistent behavior from the instructor. While this design choice was intentional, future research could explore the impact of variability in instructor behavior on task performance. Furthermore, incorporating a confirmatory visual cue for correct task execution

in the interface could enhance confidence for both the user and the instructor, ensuring smoother task progression. Additionally, while the study focused on gaze-based cues, future work could include incorporating hand gestures as a complementary or alternative referential strategy. Lastly, expanding the complexity of tasks and/or environments could help align these findings with more practical applications of gaze-based interfaces in AR collaboration.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Mixed reality toolkit 3. Available at: <https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/windows/mixed-reality/mrtk-unity/mrtk3-overview/>. Accessed: 2024-12-18. 3
- [2] Netcode for gameobjects. Available at: <https://docs-multiplayer.unity3d.com/netcode/current/about/>. Accessed: 2024-12-18. 3
- [3] Unity engine. Available at: <https://unity.com/products/unity-engine>. Accessed: 2024-12-18. 3
- [4] Universal windows platform. Available at: <https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/windows/uwp/>. Accessed: 2024-12-18. 3
- [5] A. Acar, J. Atoum, A. Reed, Y. Li, N. Kavoussi, and J. Y. Wu. Intra-operative gaze guidance with mixed reality. *Healthcare Technology Letters*, 11(2-3):85–92, 2024. 2
- [6] S. Andrist, M. Gleicher, and B. Mutlu. Looking coordinated: Bidirectional gaze mechanisms for collaborative interaction with virtual characters. In *Proceedings of the 2017 CHI conference on human factors in computing systems*, pp. 2571–2582, 2017. 2
- [7] R. Assaf, D. Mendes, and R. Rodrigues. Cues to fast-forward collaboration: A survey of workspace awareness and visual cues in xr collaborative systems. 2024. 1
- [8] H. Bai, P. Sasikumar, J. Yang, and M. Billinghurst. A user study on mixed reality remote collaboration with eye gaze and hand gesture sharing. In *Proceedings of the 2020 CHI conference on human factors in computing systems*, pp. 1–13, 2020. 1, 2
- [9] G. Bataille, A. Lammini, and J.-R. Chardonnet. Arpuzzle: Evaluating the effectiveness of collaborative augmented reality. In *2023 IEEE International Symposium on Mixed and Augmented Reality (ISMAR)*, pp. 642–651. IEEE, 2023. 1
- [10] L. Brägger, L. Baumgartner, K. Koebel, J. Scheidegger, and A. Çöltekin. Interaction and visualization design considerations for gaze-guided communication in collaborative extended reality. *ISPRS Annals of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences*, 4:205–212, 2022. 2
- [11] L. Chen, Y. Liu, Y. Li, L. Yu, B. Gao, M. Caon, Y. Yue, and H.-N. Liang. Effect of visual cues on pointing tasks in co-located augmented reality collaboration. In *Proceedings of the 2021 ACM Symposium on Spatial User Interaction, SUI '21*. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 2021. doi: 10.1145/3485279.3485297 2
- [12] S. D'angelo and B. Schneider. Shared gaze visualizations in collaborative interactions: Past, present and future. *Interacting with Computers*, 33(2):115–133, 2021. 1, 2
- [13] M. De Cecco, A. Luchetti, I. Butaslac III, F. Pilla, G. M. A. Guandalini, J. Bonavita, M. Mazzucato, and K. Hirokazu. Sharing augmented reality between a patient and a clinician for assessment and rehabilitation in daily living activities. *Information*, 14(4):204, 2023. 1
- [14] D. A. Delgado and J. Ruiz. Evaluation of shared-gaze visualizations for virtual assembly tasks. In *2024 IEEE Conference on Virtual Reality and 3D User Interfaces Abstracts and Workshops (VRW)*, pp. 765–766. IEEE, 2024. 1, 2
- [15] S. Feng, W. He, Q. Zhang, M. Billinghurst, L. Yang, S. Zhang, and X. Zhang. Arcoa: using the ar-assisted cooperative assembly system

- to visualize key information about the occluded partner. *International Journal of Human-Computer Interaction*, 39(18):3556–3566, 2023. 2
- [16] S. Feng, W. He, X. Zhang, M. Billinghurst, and S. Wang. A comprehensive survey on ar-enabled local collaboration. *Virtual Reality*, 27(4):2941–2966, 2023. 1
- [17] J. Gower, J. Baumeister, B. H. Thomas, and J. Zucco. Augmented reality annotations in a collaborative time-critical task. In *2023 IEEE International Symposium on Mixed and Augmented Reality Adjunct (ISMAR-Adjunct)*, pp. 631–636. IEEE, 2023. 2
- [18] J. E. Hanna and S. E. Brennan. Speakers’ eye gaze disambiguates referring expressions early during face-to-face conversation. *Journal of Memory and Language*, 57(4):596–615, 2007. 3
- [19] S. G. Hart and L. E. Staveland. Development of nasa-tlx (task load index): Results of empirical and theoretical research, 1988. *Advances in Human Psychology: Human Mental Workload*. Elsevier Science, 1988. 4
- [20] A. Jing. The impact of gaze cues in mixed reality collaborations. In *2021 IEEE International Symposium on Mixed and Augmented Reality Adjunct (ISMAR-Adjunct)*, pp. 473–475. IEEE, 2021. 1, 2
- [21] A. Jing, K. Gupta, J. McDade, G. A. Lee, and M. Billinghurst. Comparing gaze-supported modalities with empathic mixed reality interfaces in remote collaboration. In *2022 IEEE International Symposium on Mixed and Augmented Reality (ISMAR)*, pp. 837–846. IEEE, 2022. 1, 2
- [22] A. Jing, K. May, G. Lee, and M. Billinghurst. Eye see what you see: Exploring how bi-directional augmented reality gaze visualisation influences co-located symmetric collaboration. *Frontiers in Virtual Reality*, 2:79, 2021. 1, 2, 3, 4
- [23] A. Jing, K. May, B. Matthews, G. Lee, and M. Billinghurst. The impact of sharing gaze behaviours in collaborative mixed reality. *Proceedings of the ACM on Human-Computer Interaction*, 6(CSCW2):1–27, 2022. 1, 2
- [24] A. Jing, K. W. May, M. Naem, G. Lee, and M. Billinghurst. Eyemrvis: Using bi-directional gaze behavioural cues to improve mixed reality remote collaboration. In *Extended Abstracts of the 2021 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, pp. 1–7, 2021. 1, 2
- [25] S. Kim, M. Billinghurst, and K. Kim. Multimodal interfaces and communication cues for remote collaboration, 2020. 1
- [26] S. Kim, A. Jing, H. Park, S.-h. Kim, G. Lee, and M. Billinghurst. Use of gaze and hand pointers in mixed reality remote collaboration. In *The 9th International Conference on Smart Media and Applications. SMA, Jeju, Republic of Korea*, pp. 1–6, 2020. 2
- [27] S. Kim, A. Jing, H. Park, G. A. Lee, W. Huang, and M. Billinghurst. Hand-in-air (hia) and hand-on-target (hot) style gesture cues for mixed reality collaboration. *IEEE Access*, 8:224145–224161, 2020. 3
- [28] G. A. Koulieris, K. Akşit, M. Stengel, R. K. Mantiuk, K. Mania, and C. Richardt. Near-eye display and tracking technologies for virtual and augmented reality. In *Computer Graphics Forum*, vol. 38, pp. 493–519. Wiley Online Library, 2019. 2
- [29] B. Marques, S. Silva, A. Teixeira, P. Dias, and B. S. Santos. A vision for contextualized evaluation of remote collaboration supported by ar. *Computers & Graphics*, 102:413–425, 2022. 2
- [30] B. Marques, A. Teixeira, S. Silva, J. Alves, P. Dias, and B. S. Santos. A critical analysis on remote collaboration mediated by augmented reality: Making a case for improved characterization and evaluation of the collaborative process. *Computers & Graphics*, 102:619–633, 2022. 2
- [31] A. I. Molina, C. Bravo, J. Gallardo, C. Lacave, and M. A. Redondo. Awareness support in collaborative programming tools: An evaluation based on programmer’s perception and eye tracking. *Journal of Systems and Software*, 220:112276, 2025. 2
- [32] N. Pathmanathan, T. Rau, X. Yang, A. S. Calepso, F. Amtsberg, A. Menges, M. Sedlmair, and K. Kurzhals. Eyes on the task: Gaze analysis of situated visualization for collaborative tasks. In *2024 IEEE Conference Virtual Reality and 3D User Interfaces (VR)*, pp. 785–795. IEEE, 2024. 2
- [33] P. Renner and T. Pfeiffer. Attention guiding techniques using peripheral vision and eye tracking for feedback in augmented-reality-based assistance systems. In *2017 IEEE symposium on 3D user interfaces (3DUI)*, pp. 186–194. IEEE, 2017. 2
- [34] P. Renner and T. Pfeiffer. Attention guiding using augmented reality in complex environments. In *2018 IEEE Conference on Virtual Reality and 3D User Interfaces (VR)*, pp. 771–772. IEEE, 2018. 2
- [35] F. Sarri, L. Ragia, A. Panagiotopoulou, and K. Mania. Location-aware augmented-reality for predicting sea level rise in situ. In *2022 International Conference on Interactive Media, Smart Systems and Emerging Technologies (IMET)*, pp. 1–8. IEEE, 2022. 2
- [36] A. Schäfer, G. Reis, and D. Stricker. A survey on synchronous augmented, virtual, andmixed reality remote collaboration systems. *ACM Computing Surveys*, 55(6):1–27, 2022. 1
- [37] F. Shuo, L. Yizhe, Z. Qianrui, H. Weiping, Z. Xiaotian, W. Shuxia, and B. Mark. Parallel or cross? effects of two collaborative modes on augmented reality co-located operations. *International Journal of Human-Computer Interaction*, 2023. doi: 10.1109/ISMAR-Adjunct57072.2022.00035 1
- [38] T. T. M. Tran, S. Brown, O. Weidlich, M. Billinghurst, and C. Parker. Wearable augmented reality: research trends and future directions from three major venues. *IEEE Transactions on Visualization and Computer Graphics*, 2023. 2
- [39] T. Wagner, T. Hirzle, A. Huckauf, and E. Rukzio. Exploring gesture and gaze proxies to communicate instructor’s nonverbal cues in lecture videos. In *Extended Abstracts of the 2023 CHI conference on human factors in computing systems*, pp. 1–7, 2023. 2
- [40] X. Xu, A. Puggioni, D. Kilroy, and A. G. Campbell. User experience of collaborative co-located mixed reality: a user study in teaching veterinary radiation safety rules. In *2023 IEEE International Symposium on Mixed and Augmented Reality (ISMAR)*, pp. 583–590. IEEE, 2023. 1
- [41] S. Zhao, S. Cheng, and C. Zhu. 3d gaze vis: Sharing eye tracking data visualization for collaborative work in vr environment. In *CCF Conference on Computer Supported Cooperative Work and Social Computing*, pp. 610–621. Springer, 2022. 2